

Supplemental Figure 1

Frequent blood sampling studies in 10 arhinia patients demonstrating apulsatile LH profiles in all patients.

See main text Figure 1 for female patient #11 and Tables 1A and 1B for associated estradiol, testosterone, and inhibin B levels.

Male #1

Male #2

Male #3

Male #4

Male #5

Female #6

Female #7

Female #8

Female #9

Female #10

